

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsAAISHA NIHALA T bearing USN6SU21CP801 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC . Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsAYSHA REEHA K bearing USN6SU21CP802 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC . Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsDEVADATHAN J bearing USN6SU21CP803 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC . Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsJOHN JOSEPH bearing USN6SU21CP805 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC . Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MONICA RAO bearing USN6SU21CP806 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC . Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsNAVYA B MURALI bearing USN6SU21CP807 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC . Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsRASHMI G V bearing USN6SU21CP808 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC . Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSANIKA S bearing USN6SU21CP809 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC . Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHWAJEET S bearing USN6SU21CP810 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC . Clinical Psychology programme for the academic year 2021-2022

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